

ISSN: 2181-1040
DOI: 10.26739/2181-1040
tadqiqot.uz/renaissance

JCAR

**JOURNAL OF CENTRAL
ASIAN RENAISSANCE**

**VOLUME 4 |
ISSUE 2**

2023

МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖИЛД 4, СОН 2

ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ
ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 2

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ISSN: 2181-1040

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ**ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ
JOURNAL OF CENTRAL ASIAN RENAISSANCE****Madaeva Shahnoza Amanullaevna**Head of the Department Philosophy and Logics
of National University of Uzbekistan, DSc, Professor**PLACE OF SUFISM AND HANAFI SCHOOLS IN THE HISTORY OF THE UZBEK
IDENTITY** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252840>**ANNOTATION**

Tracing the current appearance of the traditional society of the region, which expressed the intertwining of national and religious identities, one wonders what were the historical prerequisites for this identification and what mechanisms were important factors in the formation of the religious identification of modern Uzbek society. The purpose of this study is to identify the historical roots of religious identification of traditional society. The main focus is on studying the role of the Hanafi and Sufi traditions in the formation of the mentality of the people and the mechanisms of government. The weakening of the institution of Hanafism as a result of the changing nature of the religious factor in modern Uzbekistan is also analyzed.

Key words: Islam, madhhab, Hanafi, Sufi tradition, mentality, traditions, identity, national state.

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**ЎЗБЕК ИДЕНТИКЛИГИ ТАРИХИДА ТАСАВВУФ ВА ҲАНАФИЙ МАЗҲАБИ
МАКТАБЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Худуднинг миллий ва диний ўзига хослик уйғунлигини ифода этган анъанавий жамиятининг замонавий қиёфасини кузатар эканмиз, бу идентификациянинг тарихий шароити қандай бўлган ва замонавий ўзбек жамиятининг диний идентификациясини шакллантиришда қандай механизмлар муҳим омил бўлган, деган савол туғилади. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади анъанавий жамиятдаги диний идентификациянинг тарихий илдизларини аниқлашдир. Асосий эътибор ҳанафийлик ва сўфийлик анъаналарининг халқ тафаккурини шакллантиришдаги ўрни ва бошқарув механизмларини ўрганишга қаратилган. Ҳозирги Ўзбекистонда диний омил табиатининг ўзгариши натижасида ҳанафийлик институтининг заифлашиши ҳам таҳлил қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: Ислом, ҳанафия мазҳаби, сўфийлик анъаналари, менталитет, анъаналар, идентиклик, миллий давлатчилик.

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МЕСТО СУФИЗМА И ХАНАФИТСКИХ ШКОЛ В ИСТОРИИ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Прослеживая современный облик традиционного общества региона, выразившего переплетение национальной и религиозной идентичности, задаешься вопросом, каковы были исторические предпосылки этой идентификации и какие механизмы явились важными факторами формирования религиозной идентификации современного узбекского общества. Целью данного исследования является выявление исторических корней религиозной идентификации традиционного общества. Основное внимание уделяется изучению роли ханафитских и суфийских традиций в формировании менталитета народа и механизмов управления. Также анализируется ослабление института ханафизма в результате изменения характера религиозного фактора в современном Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: ислам, ханафитский мазхаб, суфийская традиция, менталитет, традиции, идентичность, национальное государство.

Introduction. Contemporary issues of social identity today are very complex and multi-layered. Until this time, identity formation existed harmoniously with historical, social, cultural, religious, gender and other issues, but the global technologies of the third millennium brought new methods to the natural factors of identity formation. Literally the third millennium was the era of industrialization of human consciousness, and through consciousness various layers, groups, and personalities were created. Distant influences through virtual, electronic, online existence have changed the social reality of human existence in the third millennium.

Among modern influence technologies, the most “effective” method is the manipulation by religion as a tool, and this method is widely used among the Islamic population in the 21st century. In particular, in the period after Uzbekistan gained independence, the traditions of the Hanafi madhab, formed according to a special law of thinking over thousands of years, were changed, serious mental segments appeared that changed traditions, customs and rituals way of life and mental identity of the Uzbek people [1].

The purpose of this article is to study the traditions of the Hanafi madhab, which have gained great importance in statehood, sociocultural, political, legal and economic history of the Uzbek people, and its connection with Sufism, as well as the mechanisms of introduction. These characteristics systematized the principles of religious, legal, cultural and political life on the historical territory of Uzbekistan for almost a thousand years.

Methods and methodology. The fact is that the history of the introduction and spread of Hanafi in Central Asia is difficult to prove with one work and scientific views alone. Despite the fact that this topic is very important for the development of Central Asia, which is developing under the influence of religion, it began to be studied seriously only in the last decade.

The reason for the delay in research is not inattention or indifference to this topic, but the networks underlying it related topics go back to the controversial and complex aspects of Islam, the issue of organizing a comprehensive study, and the dispersion of sources.

Another reason that creates difficulty in studying the history of Hanafy in Central Asia is that it is interconnected with the history of the fundamental pillars of Islam, such as Sharia, Sufism, jurisprudence, theology, as well as with their natural roots and their complex relationships.

The history of the creation of works related to Hanafia in Central Asia was studied in the source studies of A.Muminov [2], X.Aminov [3], and S.Primov. In recent years, scholar’s and researchers of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan have defended several dissertations on Hanafi source studies.

Results and discussion. These scientific works have a historical, source-based nature, and the necessary questions of what role these two schools played in the development of the Uzbek people, and what they created, should pave the way for philosophical research. In addition, because the analysis of Islamic source studies is subject to a certain pattern, there are many situations where it is not possible to comment on the aspects of social importance for the modern period that can be concluded from the research.

But in the part of Uzbekistan, which is strongly connected with the Islamic factor of Central Asia, Hanafi madhab is not a phenomenon that can be understood in the sense of a simple sect. Hanafi madhab acted as a mechanism that effectively synthesized culture, law, science, and economic relations in the development of society. Sufism as its spiritual basis, jurisprudence as a legal regulator, and intellectual aspects were a unique construction developed on the basis of theology. It is also clear that this construction is becoming dysfunctional in modern life.

Hanafi madhab and Sufism are the roots of the historical connection, a harmonious, mutually reinforcing system. Scholar I. Usmonov explain that, “by the end of the 10th and beginning of the 11th centuries, the formation of the mystical tradition came to an end. A large amount of mystical apologetic literature was written during this period. In the 10th -11th centuries, dozens of Tabaqat works of theoretical and practical significance were published, which covered science and Sufism to varying degrees. In them, from the words of authoritative scientists, the terms of Sufism, the essence of karamat, the rules of tradition, and order within the Sufi community were explained. All the works of this period represent an attempt to prove that Sufism is on the right path and to respond to criticism from Sunni scholars. They tried to show that the activities of the first Sufis were fully consistent with the teachings of the leaders of Islamic law and aqida - Abu Hanifa, Hasan Basri, Sufyan Savri, Shofei and Ashari” [4].

Although at the beginning of Sufism there were several Sufis in Kufa, Basra, Baghdad and Syria as the main spiritual support of Islam as Hasan Al-Basri and his followers [5], but the narratives connecting Sufism and Hanafia are related to the name of Tustari.

At the heart of these two teachings are narratives about the creation of Muhammad's soul by Allah and the related concept of Muhammad's seal. The source of this narrative is associated with the name of Abu Muhammad Sahl Bin Abdullah Tustari, an important figure in the history of Islam and Sufism [6].

However, it is interesting that despite the fact that Hanafi madhab and Sufism are one whole mechanism shaping the history of Central Asia, other than this narrative there is no solid fact hinting at their common role in this region. As Ashurbek Muminov noted, such a feature of Islam as the lack of division between scholastic theology itself (kalam) and religious rights (fiqh) is not taken into account. For this reason, the theological views of many traditionalists (muhaddisun), Muslim jurists (fuqaho), ascetics (zukhhod) set out in numerous collections of hadith, works on fiqh, remain unexplored [2].

Melcherd, summing up the results of the past stage of research into the theological and legal school of Abu Hanifa, noted that despite the presence of a large amount of biographical material, it is still difficult to trace the history of regional schools, especially in Khorosan in Central Asia. The reason for the remaining ambiguities lies, in his opinion, in the fact that the Hanafis themselves paid less attention to recording their history than the Shafi'is and Malokits, or Jabarites [7].

If we pay attention to the history of the Hanafi madhab and its path, then the madhab, in understanding social problems based on the norms of Islam, followed the path of the rai method. This method is due to the fact that “in the first centuries of Islam, when Muslim dogma and law were at the stage of their development, Hanafia, unlike the other three madhhabs, occupied a more advanced position, since its teachers, following the example of Abu Hanifa, observed as much as the letter of the Koran and the Sunnah, as they sought to correspond to their spirit.

This spirit was defined by such concepts as “hukm” (paradise) and “qiyas”, therefore the Hanafis were also called “ashab ar-rai” or “ahl al-qiyas”, that is, supporters of independent opinion or comparison.

Rai - ashobul rai - independent opinions were expressed, and in their discussions the comparative-logical method of thinking prevailed. In the Hanafi madhab, these methods demonstrate the degree of accurate and objective observance of hadith in the sahih part. In Central Asia, Hanafia and its rational school emerge in methodological unity with the Maturidi direction, which leads to the emergence in this territory of a scientific, systematic institutional approach to the sources of the religion of Islam. Scientific research notes that the relationship between the traditions of the Hanafi school and maturidia is determined by its further transition to Central Asia.

Here, the special attentions is to be given to utilization of the logical rational method of the Ashab-ul-Rai school for analysis of the Islam Shari'a bases of Sufism and Hanafi. Rai – Ashab-ul-Rai – were adepts of independent thinking, the logical comparative thinking method was the lead in their discourse. Mastering of the methods secured the high clarity, impartiality, and deep observational approach in the sahih (authentic) parts of Hadiths. In the Central Asia, the methodological unity of Hanafi and its rational school Maturidia shaped the scientific, systemic institute in approaching the sources of Islam religion in this region. In the Hanafi madhab, the logical methods are present allowing to prevent turning the bases of religion towards fanaticism and radicalism under human influence, that secured progressive features of the religion of Islam in such areas as knowledge, economy, and gender relations.

Another important point in Hanafia is that, complementing the fundamental foundations of Islam with Istikhson and Urf, Hanafi madhab strictly applied all the positive foundations of local customs in Sharia.

Academician Bartold also noted the existence in Central Asia - in the region of complete predominance of the Hanafi madhab - of stable traditions in the religious sciences: “if representatives of the exact sciences were invited from Persia, then the Muslim Theological School was entirely based on local traditions in which, in addition to features characteristic of the entire Muslim world, they presented and local features [8].

In the 12th -13thcenturies, the activities of Central Asian faqehs contributed to the deeper penetration of Islam into the national culture and mentality, turning it into their religion. In turn, the scientific work of representatives of the Central Asian school became a qualitatively new stage in the further detailing and codification of the main provisions of the Hanafi mathhab.

One of the main traditions in Hanafia is “moderate Islam”. This principle was formed in order to ensure the practicality of Islam. It is in the modern period, when the true rules of Hanafi Islam in Uzbekistan are little traced, that one can trace today that the population is completely falling into Islam, the radically fundamental attitude has also increased significantly accordingly. It was moderate Islam that was the key to preventing radical fanaticism in Central Asia.

Hanafi madhab, as a teaching, finally took shape in the works of four students of the great Imam Abu Hanifa - Abu Yusuf, Abdullah Bin Mubarak Al-Marwaz, Muhammad al-Shaybani and Abu Mansur Maturidi. Each of these students contributed to the development of ideas that substantiate the political behavior of the Hanafis: “Muhammad al-Shaybani, given the importance of recognizing the freedom of choice of a person not only to take an active life position and take responsibility for his actions, but also in the spread of Islam, reveals in detail the social nature of the individual. Another student, Abu-Mansur Maturidi, using an innumerable number of facts and sources, makes it an important requirement that in ideological matters a person, not limiting himself to divine revelations, must rely on his own experience and reason. In a word, in the works of Abu Hanif's students, his ideas were further developed, setting a person up only for faith and blocking various doctrinal attitudes aimed at manipulating his consciousness” [9].

Also, with the harmonization of the social life of Hanafia with the sources of the dogma of Islam, the introduction of such methods as adat and istikhson made it possible to connect national traditions with religion in those countries where Islam came.

At the same time, methods were mobilized that preempted the intervention of the human factor.

Despite Uzbekistan being a secular state, the influence of the religion of Islam was strong in the development of the national identity, economic and cultural development. At present, the mental

stereotypes in the social, cultural, and everyday life and behavior are seen boldly. 2) The nation-building and economic roots are associated with the Islamic jurisprudence (fiqh), the regulations of the Hanafi madhab that are its basis. Besides, Sufi tariqas supported Hanafi madhab as the core of the Sharia and enriched its spiritual and supersubstantial aspects. Sufism came into being separately from Hanafi, it was a mystic practice legitimized in Islam. But in the course of historical development, it accepted the principles of Hanafi madhhab that can be seen through examples of Kubrawiyya, Qadiriyya, Khwajagan Naqshbandiyya in the Central Asia. In particular, we see Sufism and Hanafi madhhab as two main forces in the state governance at the times of the Amir Temur empire. Central Asia's nation- and indemnity-building in the economic, political, and spiritual life is rooted in Islamic jurisprudence (fiqh), Sufism, rational theology schools regularities based on Hanafi.

Conclusion. After the 20th century, the Uzbekistan's policy associated with the Islamic factor started to bring the Islamic trends aimed at other objectives and politically oriented Islam as compared to the traditional Islamic values such as Sufism and Hanafi. The values of these two systems were as follows: based on the principles of "moderate Islam", in worldview issues, not limited only to divine revelations, one should rely on one's own experience and reason. Hanafi madhab and Sufism recognized the freedom of human will, the requirement to be tolerant of other points of view and religions, and when interpreting the Qur'an, proceed from the universal technologies developed in theology and philosophy contained in such prerequisites as Qiyas, Ijma, Urf and Istikhsan.

This resulted in slow changes in the culture of society, the religious world outlook, and finally, in the principles of nation-building during the short period of the Uzbekistan's independence. The reason for this is that the historical lessons show us that religion does not change, but the principles influencing its cultural elements are prone to change. In the Central Asia, in Uzbekistan in particular that are engaged in the history of Islam, its traditions shaped by the Hanafi madhab, the plane believers note as well that, although the Islam is intact here, but its traditions and cultural principles are fully transformed. In Uzbekistan, the factor of the modern Islam changes the life style of population, dress culture, national religious ways and habits, mechanisms influencing the state governance and even the thinking style of population. Exactly therefore, the topic of Hanafi is not so much religious or historical one, but up-to-date one.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖИЛД 4, СОН 2

ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF CENTRAL ASIAN RENAISSANCE

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 2

ЎШБУ ЖУРНАЛ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ ТОМОНИДАН МОЛИЯЛАШТИРИЛГАН ИЛ-4821891548 “ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАҲДИД ВА ДАЪВАТЛАР ШАРОИТИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ВА БЕЛАРУСЬ ЁШЛАРИ ОНГИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-МАДАНИЙ ВА АКSIОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ” НОМЛИ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬ ЛОЙИҲА ДОИРАСИДА НАШРГА ТАЙЁРЛАНГАН.

THIS JOURNAL PREPARED FOR PUBLICATION AS PART OF THE INNOVATIVE SCIENTIFIC PROJECT NO. IL-4821891548 "SOCIO-CULTURAL AND AXIOLOGICAL BASES OF CONSCIOUSNESS FORMATION OF THE YOUTHS OF UZBEKISTAN AND BELARUS IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERN THREAT AND CHALLENGES", FUNDED BY THE MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

ДАННИЙ ЖУРНАЛ ПОДГОТОВЛЕН К ИЗДАНИЮ В РАМКАХ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОГО НАУЧНОГО ПРОЕКТА ИЛ-4821891548 “СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ И АКSIОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЗНАНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ ЎЗБЕКИСТАНА И БЕЛАРУСИ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УГРОЗ И ВЫЗОВОВ”

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